

The First Responder of the Future

A Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) for Collaborative Response, increasing protection and augmenting operational capacity

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Facts & Figures

INGENIOUS partners

- SU-DRS02-2018 topic: **Technologies for first responders**
- Duration: September 2019 – August 2022
- Overall budget: €8.961.111,25
 - EU contribution: €8.616.111,25
 - KR contribution: € 345.000,00
- Requested funding: *funded as requested*
- Consortium: **23 partners** and covers a large portion of Europe (12 MS and associated countries as well as the Republic of Korea, at a total of **13 countries**)
 - **6** End-users/First Responders
 - **7** Specialised SMEs and Industries
 - **1** Legal, privacy, ethical and social, human and security factors expert
 - **9** RTOs and UNIs
- Training, Testing and Validation Programme: **24** Laboratory sessions, **24** small scale field tests, **2** large scale field demonstrators/exercises

Challenges & Motivation

- Today's First Responders (FRs) are using **technology of the past**.
- FRs deal with life-threatening situations, hazardous environments, uncharted surroundings and **limited awareness**.
- **Threats and hazards evolve rapidly**, crossing municipalities, regions and nations with speed and ease.
- They are often faced with "silo-ed" operations and **overwhelming information flows**. This **should be dramatically reduced**.

- **Armouring public safety services** with all the tools that modern technology has to offer is critical.
- Tools should holistically enhance protection and augment operational capacities, **assisting them in saving lives and ensuring their safe return**.
- In the field:
 - Intelligent, integrated, interconnected and seamless tools & services that **add layers of protection** against the dangers of their working environment and
 - **augment their situational awareness** rather than distracting them from their mission.

At a glance

INGENIOUS will develop, integrate, test, deploy, demonstrate and validate a **Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) for Collaborative Response**, which ensures **high level of Protection & Augmented Operational Capacity** to respond to the disaster scene.

Armours FRs with novel, affordable and reliable tools and services as part of their **uniform** and as part of their **operational assets**.

INGENIOUS Technology

1. The NGIT builds upon the concept of **“smart” first responders** by holistically equipping them to protect them and assist in conducting their response duties, empowering and enhancing their **helmet, uniform, boots** and accompanying **K9 units with wearables, communication and localisation components, sensors and add-ons** delivering augmented reality functions.

2. The NGIT comprises of **smart devices in the air and on the ground**, that are essentially external response modules operated by first responders to **monitor, map, analyse and assess the incident scene**;

- the fully customisable self-exploring drones - **Multi-purpose Autonomous eXploring drone** and **Micro Indoor drone**,
- the standalone components for delivering **ubiquitous worksite comms**,
- the **indoor and outdoor localisation modules** used to track & trace FRs and their proximity to team members, victims, assets, risks, hazards in real time.

3. The NGIT supports FRs with **multi-fusion and expert reasoning modules** for improving **situational awareness and threat and hazard detection**, a **C3 and a COP platform** with augmented reality capabilities as add-ons for **Command, Control and Coordination** and with **mobile applications** to improve response activities.

fully aware, fully connected and fully integrated

“Smart” First Responders

Tools & Services to protect them and enhance operational tasks

FRs NGIT Components

- Helmet
- Uniform & wearables
- Boots
- K9 Units

- **Protecting FRs:** Cameras (HD, Thermal/IR), Gas sensors, Environmental sensors, Acoustic sensors, Vital sensors (monitoring biometrics), Location sensors, On board processing power, multi-RF comms,...
- **Augmenting their situational awareness:** Knowing position of hazards, team members and assets, communications between members and victims, connected with AR glasses, various tools and services (MAX, MIN)
- **Allowing them to collaboratively respond:** Common Operational Picture, FR mobile applications and C2

Uniform integration platform

Helmet & comms

Bracelet

Insole boot component

“Smart” Devices in the Air and on the Ground

Tools & Services operated by First Responders to protect them and enhance operational tasks

Smart devices in the air and in the ground

- Micro Indoor droNe (Deployable Positioning System)
- Multi-purpose Autonomous eXploring drone (monitoring & detecting)
- Field comms

High level design of MAX

MINs swarm formation to improve indoor localisation

MAX platforms will be able to enter from openings of various structures and **navigate autonomously** indoors, collecting 2D and 3D data of unexplored areas. MAX offers multi-task exploration at the worksite(s) level – **indoors and outdoors** as it delivers: A multitude of sensors.

Collision based navigation in cluttered, unknown environments

Personal Area Networks (low-power, short-range to interconnect FRs with their body gear and with team members and assets in proximity),
Local Area Networks (low-power, mid-range interconnecting FRs and assets with the local command-post) and
Wide Area Networks (wide range to interconnect worksite resources and local command-post with the C2 centre)

Information Management, Augmenting the Common Operational Picture, C2 & FR Apps (1/2)

- Multi Information Fusion Module (*Data exploitation and decision making*)
- Augmented Reality Environment Services

Intuitive contextual notifications

- Display of sensor values and situational information
- Location of team members, hazardous areas, practitioners, mission target
- Visualisation of AR checklists pinned to the worksite location
- Remote assistance by an expert

Augmented Reality (AR) functions

- Define and implement the **integration of multiple sources**, fusing data at different abstraction levels to **achieve context awareness and detect patterns** that suggest more complicated circumstances.
- INGENIOUS **Early Warning System (EWS)** providing real-time situational awareness and decision support (extraction of **conclusions** concerning environmental and first responder's behaviour aspects, **early detection** of unusual events or patterns).

Information Management, Augmenting the Common Operational Picture, C2 & FR Apps (2/2)

- Mobile Application Kit: Face recognition, Triage & Patient tracking, Multilingual, Social media and Worksite Operations Applications
- Common Operational Picture (COP) & Command & Control (C2)

Social Media App: Crawl data from social media and online content to assist FRs. Spot nearby **critical situations that have been reported** (filtering out fake news).

Multi-lingual operations App: Development of a multi-lingual communication support application that will comprise a **speech-to-speech translation module** to enhance voice communications (multilingual COPs, FR teams, different FR teams).

Worksite App: A mobile app digitising **worksite operations** (INSARAG compliant forms with appropriate classification levels and forms completion) for making them faster, organized and more efficient (**day-to-day logistics and resources management, casualty management** and exploiting machine learning algorithms to train the system providing **state-of-the-art decision support** functionalities).

Face Recognition App: Based on cutting-edge deep learning technologies. **Patient recognition and correlation to the medical data** (within the triage app, for quick triaging). Input data through the AR glasses (from the helmet) or the cameras (uniform and UAVs). **Resilient to face injuries.**

Create an innovative **COP** to be **shared by all involved actors**. The COP will be generated assimilating **information from all sensors as well as from data fusion and expert reasoning engines**. COP is part of a modern **C3**.

Triage and Patients Tracking App: It concerns the development of a mobile app coupled with the appropriate hardware (RF-based – NFC, BT- changing colours via LED bracelets) for **assisting FRs conducting triage and pre-hospitalisation support** of the affected population in a worksite. Unique identification of patients/victims **from extraction time to transport at the nearest hospital**.

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Toolkit Integration, Testing & Field Validation and Knowledge Capitalisation

A rich programme that contains:

- 24 Laboratory Integration and Testing sessions (LITs),
- 24 Command Post/Small Scale Field Tests (CP/SSTs) and
- 2 Large Scale Field Validation demonstrators/exercises (FSXs)

of the Toolkit's integrated components, platforms, modules and applications, promoting **close collaboration of technologists with practitioners**

FRs will have to respond to several combinations of cases in several scales - standalone or in parallel – with or without cascading effects

- [Industrial accident, Building fire]
- [Earthquake/Explosion damaged building, Flooded enclosed space/Maritime SAR]
- [Earthquake/Explosion damaged building, Fire covering large rural/forestry area]
- [Earthquake/Explosion damaged building, Flooded enclosed space]
- [Earthquake/Explosion damaged block of buildings, Flooded wide area and enclosed space]
- [Absence of comms after disastrous event, worksite and indoor comms between FRs, with victims to the HQ/Maritime SAR]
- [Earthquake/Explosion damaged building]
- [Triaging after large earthquake/explosion]
- [Attack in public space, Patient biometrics after triaging in earthquake]
- [Large earthquake near shore with cascading effects, e.g. chemical leakage, comms failure]
- [* attacks in multiple locations]

Target Markets/Stakeholders

A search team managed to rescue an earthquake survivor who needs to be brought to hospital immediately (exercise in Bulgaria). © European Union/ECHO

Practitioners (civil protection, fire brigades, emergency medical services and police services)

to be trained and validate INGENIOUS

ERCC operations, training exercise © European Union/ECHO

EU (ERCC, ECHO, JRC, CoU) & MS Ministries (Ministry of Interior, public order, civil protection)

to update policy framework and buy INGENIOUS

The general public (citizens, volunteers, special groups)

to be aware and benefit from INGENIOUS

EU Projects SU-DRSo2-2018-2019-2020 (ASSISTANCE, CURSOR, FASTER, RESPONDRONE, etc.) and **EU Crisis Management Projects**

to exchange knowledge and interface with INGENIOUS

Example systems from IN-PREP partners

Technology providers

Liaise with INGENIOUS (new business opportunities for INGENIOUS partners)

Thank you for
your attention
Any Questions ?

INGENIOUS

“INGENIOUS /ɪnˈdʒiːniəs/ {adjective}: Clever, original, and inventive. Cleverly and originally devised and well suited to its purpose.”

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